

Notation of Topophilia

Field Notes

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Foreword

'Notation of Topophilia' is a journey meant to interrogate the human obsession with place, inspired by the field of humanistic geography.

"Field Notes" is composed of 'Thoughts', 'Conversations', and 'Quotes'.

The structure of these notes aims to reveal my research process and floats between abstract and concrete, as I develop my methodology. These three sections organically knit together the structure of my empirical research process.

'Thoughts' begins with current discourses on my research topic, the meaning of places for individuals, and discusses the potential and limitations of visualisations of places. It also considers how to deal with the public through practical interactions.

The orientation of time begins with the past, but it moves towards the future. Once a thought becomes clear, other questions quickly come up, and cause the repeated deconstruction of all existing answers. Although I began this research with the motivation to gain a sense of place for myself, this journey led me to the inevitable topic of nationality. Through my working progress, I was forced to call into question many existing thoughts derived from the mono-narrative of my particular background. What ultimately became the important thing for me were these deconstructions, and the impossibility of constructing firm notions. Through these realizations, I started to seek broader notions of the concept of place.

'Conversations' are dialogues from field work of my previous projects in different cities such as Nagano, Tokyo, Berlin, Dresden. They are also a reduction, translation, derivation and explanation of phenomenological geography theories seen through people living in contemporary society.

'Quotes' are taken from various researchers in the field of geography, urban research, iconography, psychiatry, and highlight the universality of this topic despite time and cultural differences.

Shared places may suggest the future

“Thank you so much for letting me into this house,
but I need to go now, I need to go back to my place”

“Well, Grandma, here is your home.
You don't have another place to go back to,
where do you wish to go? ”

1992

My grandmother, who suffered from dementia,
often escaped from our house in the suburbs of Tokyo.
Little me was always wondering what she was thinking.

Seeking meanings of places for humans

This research poses questions about the correlations between places and human emotions. How do human beings recognise a place as a part of one's self? My aim is to take note of the emotional relationships between humans and places. While experimenting with a variety of approaches, I found research from a variety of fields of study. I am influenced by the fields of design and humanistic geography, which leads me to repeatedly return to the question "what is place?" Inspired by conversations with people, I aim to show new perspectives about place through various forms.

This research begins with human consciousness, which is comprised of internal worlds. However, these internal worlds are made up of our surrounding environments. Environments create humans, humans create environments. When taking into account people's memories, the correlation between memory and topographical space becomes clear. Consider the question: "Would you tell me about your place?" Potential answers to this question may produce stories about a region or the informant herself. It is impossible to define a clear border between the two. The ultimate aim of this research is to get to know places as mirrored by humans, as well as to get to know humans as mirrored by places. My research crosses disciplines such as environmental design and public art, and is influenced by my life in both Japan and Germany. The process of making artwork is utilised for visualising notions of place which are usually hidden in the inner worlds of individuals. The works are generated through observations and collected interviews in several target cities, and will be further explained in this text.

My initial motive is the connection with the anonymous landscape in which I grew up. I was born and brought up in a house that my parents bought in the hilly landscape in the suburbs of Tokyo, Japan. Though it felt like our house, I always felt a sense of distance to the landscape. The typical urban development strategy after the war in Japan was to create a topography of nature, to tear down mountains, to landfill, and to erase the history of the land in favor of building more and more identical houses. The original motivation was economic efficiency and managerial cohesion, and it did not consider individuals and local cultures.

I was always seeking my place. The initial motive lead me to create the first work in this research series, "About my topos." Since then, I have moved away from myself to include various subjects.

A place presupposes a personal connection to an environment. People find connections with cities and their immediate surroundings. Design gives shapes to things and is responsible for creating the future. Art is the act of inquiring about the world, rocking the fixed points, and centers around human emotions. Public is a concept that encompasses everything. Cities are an accumulation and a representation of all the culture, thought, and technology that has been produced by humans. While observing different cities and people, my interest shifted from creating deliverables to simply opening my mind to different points of view about place. This thesis shares the viewpoint of an observer.

Space, then, has been seen in distinction to place as a realm without meaning - as a 'fact of life' which, like time, produces the basic coordinates for human life. When humans invest meaning in a portion of space and then become attached to it in some way (naming is one such way) it becomes a place.

Place: An Introduction, 2014

Tim Cresswell

Space transforms into a place

The term place is differentiated from space. We are surrounded by spaces: cities, parks, courtyards, gardens, living rooms, or the corner of a bed. We live in space, however, we do not always call that space Place. One creates a place from a portion of space, by personalising it. Places have special meanings projected on them, such as experiences, feelings, and histories. Even if we could survive living in many different sites, it does not mean we have gained our own place. Place occurs at the level of all identities such as my place, your place, street, neighborhood, town, county, region, state, and continent. But locations do not correspond to such order. All of them are overlapping and intermingling, leaving availability for various interpretations.¹

The term landscape has several definitions depending on the culture in which it is used. In Japanese, the term landscape is divided into two terms. Huukei focuses on an inner landscape, while Keikann describes a visible landscape². Both terms originated from the German word "Landschaft" and are translated into English as landscape. A sense of place is closer to the skin, while a sense of landscape creates distance from the skin. Despite their distinctions, these notions are important to consider when trying to understand the relationships between humans and places.

While I was researching the emotional connection between humans and places, I encountered the text *Topophilia*³ by Yi-Fu Tuan. The term attempts to verbalise the highly varied emotional connections between humans and places. Topophilia is literally "the love of place." Tuan defines it as "the affective bond between people and places". The term "Topophilia" was the main gateway that led me to explore the depths of this topic. Since then I have been experimenting with different ways of approaching the emotional connection people have with their lived environments. The term encompasses varied phenomenon from the small scale individual experience of tactile sensation, to emotional connections, to large entities such as districts, cities, and nation states. How can we find the commonality in such individual experiences? The significance of the term is clear, but the concept is still obscure, since it is theoretically impossible to find clear answers. Thus, my research and my production are concerned with notation. When I feel lost in a labyrinth, insightful texts and meaningful conversations allow me to enjoy being lost in the fog.

While trying to analyse the ambiguous notion of "Topophilia", I will present my findings concerning the complex relationships between humans and place. I will record how people consider their own places, and what people want to gain, or be released from, in terms of space.

¹ John Donat

² Tadahiko Higuchi, Noboru Kawazoe,

³ The term was coined by the humanistic geographer Yi-Fu Tuan in the book *Topophilia: A Study of Environmental Perception, Attitudes and Values*.

Mr. Kumai, Nagano

Place : Oshida, Nagano, Japan, **Informant:** A former inhabitant of the site

“The impressiveness of the mountains around my town..?
I wouldn't rate it so high. Maybe 1 out of 5.” ”

It was in a cafe near Ochanomizu station in the city centre of Tokyo.
During lunch time, I was surrounded by dark grey business suits. As always, I was scribbling in a sketchbook while drinking a cup of coffee. An elderly man leaned over and asked me: "Do you mind doing that for me as well?"“

That was the first encounter with Mr. Kumai.

He told me has has been living and working for many years in a major company in Tokyo, but was originally born and raised in Nagano.

“I'm summarising my childhood memories about Oshida. It seems nice to have your drawings of human figures in my book because my humans look like matchsticks.”

When I opened his sketchbook, I discovered lively depictions of his life in the mountains from 70 years ago, all drawn from memory.

There were sketches of his house, which does not exist anymore, sketches of family dinners, descriptions of after school activities, family trees, and word charts of dialects. My attention gravitated more to his notebook than to his request.

“Yeah, I can draw something for you. But your book attracts me a lot, can you help me as well?”

So I traveled in Oshida with his book. Nagano is a highland area surrounded by mountains. There is a big old temple named ‘Zenkoji’ near the main train station of the prefecture. Tourism is still active around the old temple clusters. His place was on the edge between the city and one of the mountains. After 20 minutes of riding in a small old bus, the area in which he drew rice fields and apple tree farms appeared, but this time it appeared as endless housing projects. I was not able to see the world the way he expressed it, but the structure of the site with “the forest behind the habitation area, on a hill overlooking a broad landscape towards low lands” reminded me of a prototype of a pristine Japanese landscape by Higuchi Tadahiko, together with a prototype of human’s pristine nest by Edward Relf.

There was an unfillable gap between what I could see and what I had seen in his notebook.

With a little disappointment, I explored the area. I followed a narrow creek, checking name plates on houses, grave stones, and shrines to trace the world of his memory.

After my first trip, we had dozens of meetings to figure out what the most important elements of the site were, what is left, and what should become more visible. I tried to make charts of environmental elements from his memory to evaluate the characteristics of the site. I picked words and illustrated things from his book. I made pictograms according based on his impressions, listing and sorting elements to possibly symbolise the site. Then I considered the characteristics that made an impression on me that I could make more visible through my art work.

He helped me to make ratings for a list of words that I accumulated from his story. “The impressiveness of the mountains around my town..? I wouldn't rate it so high. Maybe 1 out of 5.”

He was talking and continued to rate hundreds of elements. The most highly rated elements were personal sites such as “a storage bin behind my house” “an old water milling house” “school” or special events, such as “Falling down during a mock cavalry battle” or “Driving my teacher's bike to the city”.

In my next trips, I tried to see from his perspective. I went to local museums, surveyed regional documents and old maps, then tried to see the surface of the land from his eyes. Again and again, whichever map I was using, my impression was: ‘I only see a plain surface’. From my perspective, the skyline of the mountains and the air that pours through the forest into the residential area are the only stable characteristics of the site.

In the beginning of May, after we did a small exhibition, we were standing in front of freshly growing trees. “Ah! Smiling!” That was the moment I could see something from his point of view. These words ‘Smiling Mountains’ are an expression from his book. It is a regional and seasonal expression to connote spring mountains. It represents the transitional moment from the cold winter to the beginning of spring, which is somehow different from my region. In the last meeting, with a feeling of disappointment, we were at an underground cafe in a building's forest near Tokyo station. As usual talking about places we weren't currently in. All of the sudden he said: “but.. wait, the mountain range, ah, that is the treasure for me..now I must to change the rate, from 1 to 5. even more than 5.” Then he wrote poetry and made sketches about the landscape.

I had to learn about the uncertainty of scoring and evaluating landscapes, since one cannot be aware of the unconscious influences from one's surroundings.

Artistic navigational aids in the intellectual and emotional understanding of our world

Ingo Günther

Maps are born out of a desire to see and know the appearance of the world around us. General maps aim to be objective and universal, and the relationship between a map and local details is like that between a dictionary and words: the clearer it is, the more accurate it is. Maps can also show things invisible to the naked eye, such as geological strata. By drilling according to a geological map, you can confirm the locations of hot springs and coal layers. They are part of the “hard world” that no-one doubts. Introducing a new axis is a method of capturing that undoubted hardness in a soft way, an expression of critical awareness. Drawing a map around an axis of sensations or time, for example, makes the supposedly “hard” and “universal” world look like something else altogether.

Soft maps
Kohei Sugiura

Maps and visions of place

Maps highlight power. Notation shows a vision and interaction with a site.

In the early history of cartography, the main purpose of inventing a new mapping system was to make accurate notations of space and transform the three dimensional surface of the earth into a two dimensional representation. A world map deconstructs our ball shaped planet and represents it on flat printed papers, lines mark the terrain and are meant to show geographical features on the earth's surface. People have discovered a multitude of ways to portray the earth using a variety of visualisation systems. Digital technology created a more participatory process in the field of cartography. The trend of big data visualization is a cartography of informatics. Although highly varied types of cartographic images exist, they universally show some power dynamics based on what is highlighted and what has been erased. Architectural and landscape notation systems were created for evaluating or re-discovering how humans perceive environments. Kevin Lynch's mental map influenced urban planning and served a practical function in the creation of new cities. Notations from landscape planners like Lawrence Halprin have also directly influenced planning. Of the many examples of visualisation I encountered, my initial inspiration was Kohei Sugiura's deformed maps and diagrams. His visuals show subjective, sensory views by switching points of view and questioning how one experiences the world. Additionally, Guy Debord presented the concept of "Psychogeography" through a critical approach to capitalism and power while exploring a cognitive perception of Paris. By using aesthetic tools- both abstract and poetic- his group showed some visions for changing the world.

When traveling somewhere new, I always check local printed maps . In these maps, we can glance at the structure of a space and understand something, even if we don't know the language. These maps have a clear point of view, the map shows what its creator deems important. There is regional information and official information that reflects the politics of that location. Just recently it became possible to fly around the world using maps on the Internet. Unlike in previous eras, contemporary culture creates a situation in which people are not confined to 'one world'. However, people continue to perceive the world both through regional maps and through their unconscious experiences of everyday life.

The map I have seen most of my life is the one of Japan. It shows islands surrounded by seas, and beyond the seas, the rest of the world. Europe is located on the far side of the map, or it doesn't even fit on the paper. In 2007, in a small souvenir shop in Syria near the Dead Sea, I saw the image of the world on a map that I could never have imagined. On a corner of the wall, there was the map and the Israeli territory was painted over in black. Another time, I visited a library in the Philippines and they only had maps of national resources and statistics, all from an American perspective. They did not have ordinary town maps in the public library. A librarian told me, "I have never seen a map of our city, but it may be necessary in the future."

Today, with the help of basic gadgets, everyone can make their own maps or archive their daily lives digitally, catching the essence of the locations they visit. Even though the availability of maps and types of maps has expanded dramatically, official maps are still used and still designate power. The power of the image, utilized by designers and artists, has the ability to both consciously and unconsciously manipulate a group of people. Before the war, the concept of public art in Japan was to present suitable idols and create ideal citizens. It has been used as a force to define and perpetuate a single narrative from the perspective of those at the top. Even now, there are movements that divide people into majorities and minorities, separating people into the good ones and the bad ones. I am interested in disassembling these ideas by deconstructing the topic of "places"

Through the notion of Topophilia- I will uncover the complex, multilayered nature of places and the ways in which people have influenced those places. Rather than presenting one clear narrative as an answer, I will present a collective impression of the notion of place through the exploration of a variety of disconnected places.

*Landscape is an interpretation, it is inseparable with how a man sees space.
Thus we must abandon the notion of objectivity.*

Alan Corbin
(1936-)

Landscapes are culture before they are nature; constructs of the imagination projected onto wood and water and rock. So goes the argument of this book. But it should also be acknowledged that once a certain idea of landscape, a myth, a vision, establishes itself in actual place, it has a peculiar way of muddling categories, of making metaphors more real than their referents; of becoming, in fact, part of scenery.

Simon Schama
(1945-)

Primarily, "Genfukei (original landscape)" is an individual thing, meaning each one is mine to possess. On the other hand, for those who lived in the past, "landscape" was not mere landscape but an "environment" with which they were actively interacting. This subjectively also means that each person is the same as I am.

*By looking through the Genfukei, and seeing what is mine,
I believe for the first time we can feel the activities of people in history.
One can believe in "I" as the same as another "I", all originating from the original one.*

Noboru Kawazoe
(1926-2015)

Multi-worlds interpreted

A narrative is a memory that a person shares. It is also the history of a group. What is often confusing is that history is perceived as fact, when it is merely an interpretation, which by chance happens to be "an official view." There are countless narratives. Each social group is educated by one interpretation, which is presented as evidence of fact. Other groups use different interpretations and shared histories for the same incident. There is no true fact. When a memory is shared, it is considered "fact" by the informant. That "fact" is reality for the subject. At the same time, such "facts" do not exist. It does not mean that I doubt them when I listen their stories. There is no such thing as facts from the beginning. Although it sounds like a trick, things like experiences and events accumulated as memories are edited and interpreted by the informant from the moment that event happened. At some point, I was puzzled by the differences between raw narratives and known information. It is impossible to evaluate whether something that is spoken is true or not. In essence, it is not possible to judge if what people say about their places is true or not.

Paralleled Roppongi**Place:** Roppongi, Tokyo, Japan, **Informant:** Two inhabitants

“My scenery of the city is full of greens,
there are many elegant villas belonging to feudal lords.”

The first meeting was in the Mori Building, a high rise tower in Roppongi Hills, one of the central districts in Tokyo. In this commercialised building's forest, the city is portrayed as a night city, a downtown area, and in recent years it has become more popular as an arty district, utilizing art for branding of further urban development. "Roppongi Hills" is a building complex which is called the symbolic nest of the "Modern bourgeoisie", owing to its high rents. The first task was to do something during Art Night, which was organised by the developer. Although the company is driving the huge urban development project, the one night festival is aimed at connecting locals, new residents, working people and visitors. This responds to the city's current situation as a disconnected community. After some downsizing of my project, I wrote small series of illustrated articles. One of them is called "Paralleled Roppongi."

Here I asked: "Please tell me your Roppongi" and they talked freely in narrative interviews. Then I transcribed the full text of the recorded interview and made a diagram, composed of a collage-like illustration based on what I was told. I especially concentrated on what they were trying to emphasize and convey through their impressions.

The first subject, a 95 year old woman, emphasised the landscapes of the city before it was Westernised, starting from her memories of when she moved to Roppongi, before World War II. She continued with memories of her life during wartime, and the process of recovering their lives from the burning fields. Elements of the landscape and her place which were emphasised repeatedly were "currently unseen" such as the villas of the feudal lords, the military bases, and the small trams. On the other hand, she ignored elements visible in the current city.

In listening to an informant's story, in order to tolerate listening, I try to not to interfere with my opinion as much as possible. I try to focus on the place for that person. This time, however, I asked her about her opinions on the current city and the future. She clearly rejected the landscape of the present city and stated that the past landscape was better.

Her landscape was a landscape before the big transitions, filled with greens and an un-westernised cityscape. Due to the radical destruction of the city, and urban development schemes that revamp without leaving signs of the past history, there is little continuity between the landscape of the present and that of the past. The city's current iteration is not considered real scenery for her. Yet many people see the city's current surface as the "reality of the site".

The severe disconnect between landscapes of the past, and the current city, may create more and more negative emotions. It may cause her to remain stubborn and return to the past more and more regularly.

In many cases, consumers are the focus of activity in the city. They are usable icons which represent current trends in city development, conducted by powerful developers. Ironically, people who have been living in the city longest, and have experienced the city's transitions, are outside of the reality of the modern world.

“My city? It has many empty fields where I played baseball with my classmates often. But it’s difficult to see a concrete image of the city, because I’m living here and it’s changing all the time.”

I entered into a nostalgic store for metal tools, such as kitchen pots, tiny metal brushes, and sprays to maintain these tools. I asked “Would you tell me about your city here?” and the second information provider, a 65year old man who owns the store, narrated his story about the city over the course of an hour.

In this project’s process, I recorded interviews and transcribed entire scripts based on the narratives which were told to me. Then, I picked words they had emphasized. I Literally counted the frequency of words, and then checked their usages and how they relate to certain periods of the city. For example, one site had several names in a different era, depending on the function of the building, the owners, and the meanings for individuals. People often use a previous name of a site to address the site, although the name is erased from the current maps. His narration followed a chronological order and covered the radical transition of the city. It sounded like he was trying to summarise the official history of the city for a stranger, as a representative of the city. In the beginning he described the scenery of burnt fields after the war, then he described the building process of the symbolic landmark “Tokyo Tower” during a time of rapid growth, which marked the centre of his cityscape. The Tokyo Olympics was a significant event, showing the fast recovery process, which garnered the attention of the nation. This was one of the highlighted memories for him. The street became a forest of buildings during the economic bubble. What was missing from his description was the time when the economic bubble burst. His narrative continued to discuss segregation between old inhabitants and newcomers, and the ongoing urban development.

As he grew up, his attention towards his surroundings became weak. What was emphasized again and again were his childhood memories of empty fields used as playgrounds. Like the first informant, his mind also lives in the current city based on the brownish fields with his small classmates.

While I was converting their verbal narratives into visuals, I had to face the fact that the objective evaluation of time is not synchronised with the subjective evaluation of time. This disconnect, between time on a clock, and time in the mind, alters the way people see place.

The complexity of formless elements

After someone expresses something to someone else, the images that are shared, become shared images. The information seems to be the property of the informant, however from the moment this information is released into the universe, it no longer belongs to that person. Also, when private property is converted into public space, its intended function is always dictated by someone. I focus on expressing elements that can not be expressed so clearly.

In many cases, visualized information such as diagrams are considered more accurate if they are based on data that can be processed numerically. Handling information based on human subjectivity does not meet the requirements of reliable visualization, yet that is the core of my approach. When sharing an un-graspable element, it is necessary to select a mode of expression that is not absolutely concrete.

Objective information relating to a place or a person can be the date, weather, age, and the like. On the other hand, elements that are subjective are emotions, personal interests, feelings, and strength of impression. They cannot be weighed in normal dialogue. Even if it is replaced by a number in the assumption, it is fluctuating ambiguous information.

How exactly can we handle such ambiguity? What are the desirable expressions when charting non-quantitative information: bar charts, pie charts, line graphs? These can be used under the premise that the information is confirmed. At the beginning, I tried expressing myself using such figures. But I discovered it is a trap to imitate these forms of representation. Instead I replace it with a formalized form by arbitrarily manipulating the original information. After I noticed that it is necessary to avoid using fixed values, I began to use abstract expressions which are more interpretable. I made blurred illustrations and symbols that are difficult to see at first glance to represent places and what they might mean to people.

The reason to make an abstract iconic image is to grasp the whole as a whole, and to interpret non-verbal interpretations.

It is an act of giving a provisional shape to something that does not have a form inside of one's head but expresses a landscape or a place.

Language is a symbol which expresses ethnicity, it could be said that it becomes iconic symbols. Symbols concerning places in a certain area depend on the context of the place, and it is difficult to understand the context when coming from the outside. No matter how official symbols are turned to common language, I try playing with a combination of "signifier" and "signified" in local contexts.

As I tried doing in the project in Dresden, playing with local materials is also an act of trying to understand the symbols of a site through the use of the body. It mimics the experiences of domestic life and creates a gap that appears due to the differences in understanding and interpretation.

Our everyday life-world consists of concrete “phenomena”. It consists of people, of animals, of flowers, trees and forests, of stone, earth, wood and water, of towns, streets and houses, doors, windows and furniture. And it consists of sun, moon and stars, of drifting clouds, of night and day and changing seasons. But it also comprises more intangible phenomena such as feelings. This is what is “given”, this is the “content” of our existence.

Everything else, such as atoms and molecules, numbers and all kinds of “data”, are abstractions or tools which are constructed to serve other purposes than those of everyday life.

Today it is common to give more importance to the tools than our life-world.

Genius Loci: Towards a Phenomenology of Architecture

Christian Norberg-Schulz

(1926- 2000)

Asking about your Place

When you ask someone about their place, you are asking them to reveal private information. In describing one's place, people may reveal their ethnic group, their beliefs, their temperament, and much more. Regardless of categorisation, everybody is equal in that they all seek out a place of their own. Using narratives from people and showing them as diagrams or written texts, interpreted by the observer, somehow neutralizes the information. Social researchers have created ways to categorize personality traits, and divide people according to ethnicity, location, occupation, income, and many other categories. Numerous methodologies sort humans into groups, but I prefer to focus on each individual and their unique conception of place. Although cultural background influences what one believes, it is undeniably altered when one moves between different places. This act of moving between places, or choosing to stay somewhere, tells us something about the character of the individual. Individuals float around seeking their own place until they find it.

Asking a question, one always has pre-conceived notions about what a subject will say. However, what I considered important when I had conversations with people, was that which revealed my blind spots and lead me in new directions. For the practical aspect of making work, it is inevitable that one will omit information that is inconsistent with the point of view of the work. In addition, it is obvious that asking something from others doesn't lead me to create something.

A subject tries to express that which is not graspable in his own mind by using words or sketches. When the observer tries to find some sort of clear organisation from this narrative, to create concrete answers, it is like trying to catch the fog with one's hands.

In several cities that I visited, many people expressed the desire to share their places and express themselves through "talking about places". If I had approached them as a journalist or member of the media, it is likely this reaction would change. Somehow by explaining that the purpose of my work was "Art", made people feel less judged. They didn't think I would use their information in an undesirable way. Often people are excited to express themselves and talk about places. They truly wonder at the questions stirring up in their minds, and become emotional, sometimes even to the point of tearing up. I have been frequently surprised about how people react to the topic of place. Although I am always a passive listener, I always have to remind myself not to judge their narratives. I am aware that I don't know about the many worlds my informants are telling me about.

I have adopted the following three positions and utilize these methods based on each unique experience:

- 1: Position to describe a place based on my own experiences
- 2: Position to analyse a place while observing others
- 3: Position to deconstruct and compose information about places as artworks

The act of trying to capture the intrinsic nature of place, through sketching and other artistic actions, and dismantling its meaning, is a response to the unreachable relationship between each individual and each place.

Participation observation⁴ (Becoming part of the party, living inside):

Observing fine worlds that people see that could not be formed without the passing of time.

"About my topos", "In / Visible Weimar"

Landscape observation (observation from the outside as a visitor):

Grabbing a representative image roughly. "Mr. Kumai, Nagano", "Stadt Gestalten Düsseldorf"

Interview :Verbal interaction, narrative history, listening to one person. Focusing on the informant and striving to share and understand that person's world. "Roppongi Parallels", "Mr. Kumai, Nagano", "Landscapes Narratives"

Questionnaire (multiple summaries of a simple survey): Collect multiple samples and explore views from many directions. "Portraits of Dresden"

Both the participation observation and the landscape observation are subjects themselves.

Interviews and questionnaires are trying to extract some information about each location.

I believe that the complex relationship between people and places is best expressed by going back and forth between multiple approaches. Thus I changed what I initially assumed: "that a work is a conclusion". My research process is contradictory and chaotic. I connect vastly different places, people, and events and highlight the myriad ambiguities. A dialogue about a place through customary language seems impossible. Something our conversations move beyond words and emotions, and these places become accessible beyond the cultures they inhabit.

⁴ Referring from qualitative research methods

*The earth's surface is highly varied.
But the way in which people perceive and evaluate that surface is far more varied.
No two persons see the same reality.
No two social groups make precisely the same evaluation of the environment.
But with good will one person can enter into the world of another
despite difference in age, temperament, and culture.*

Topophilia
Yi-Fu Tuan
(1930-)

A place of somebody. A landscape of somebody.

It is clear that 'my place' is not 'your place', 'your place' is not 'my place'. One cannot live in another's landscape. Once "I" see "your landscape" through "my mind", it is reflected as a collage of "my landscape".

Even though we are seeing the same thing, we see it in a different ways. Because our perception is not a physiological vision, it is already structured. The "objective world", championed by modern philosophy and science, does not exist when we consider our perception alongside another's. However, the logical part of human wisdom keeps us believing in the objective world which formed by standardised values.

I decided to make work about places that are 'not mine' in order to interfere with the image of that place, which is flexible and never fully formed. The act of production triggers, it brings something to light which was hidden. I find joy in the process of making something unknown gradually appear. A glimpse of a location, expressed through the people in the places I visited, and the ensuing dialogue makes my own world more visible to me. My further goal is to open this field of visibility to others.

The emotion one feels about a place evokes a feeling of common sense and being awake. This topic could show us what we have in common, and making artwork is an attempt at bringing sense to a chaotic world. Colors and shapes instantly represent something. Before the viewer understands what he is seeing, artwork affects the body. The messages produced by the work talk to each person as an individual entity. I do not make objects. There is a moment in which difference becomes a universal thing, and this difference is shared beyond the difference in words.

In the beginning, I was considering how to present different places in Japan, and how to show the differences and the personalities of these landscapes that seem homogenous at first. How can one visualise the diversity of places and make them shareable? In Europe, diversity and different landscapes already exist. There are organisations that research and preserve historic places such as museums. These regional museums are active today, while remaining symbols of regional identity. Every region expresses its personality according to its unique characteristics. There is also an obvious diversity, with people of different backgrounds living together.

The way to investigate a place which does not belong to me, and the purpose of this inquiry, depends on the environment, the target area, and the way of thinking there.

Topophilia assumes that commonality transcends differences, sadness, or nostalgia towards a place, and has the power to break through and create a new sense of place. I believe this notion gives a hint about how to deal with the future.

The same way that parsing meaning from architecture needs education, the physical surface of the world does not give absolute value to outsiders.

Landscapes Narratives

Place: Berlin, Germany, **Informant:** 14 people from various backgrounds

My first feelings of ignorance related to the topic of migration. These narratives taught me the reality of mobility in the globalised world and some of the reasons that cause people to leave their place.

I encountered a wealth of information that was not available to me in school or in official histories.

"My grandparents crossed the sea and settled down. You could say my mother-tongue is either Japanese or Brazilian. But it's better to speak English. One year I visited the town of my grandfather, in Japan, because it was my dream to see it. After going back and working in several cities, I came to Berlin for my partner. I want to go back there, I mean Brazil, at least every half year. "

During the entire process of collecting interviews, I was a completely passive listener. However, all of the interviews lasted over one and a half hours, and informants narrated various stories, some descriptive, some more emotional. I was shocked by the complexity of information, and the layered meanings towards place. After the interviews, and my own time in Germany, I began to understand the deep struggles of place making and choosing where to live.

"Where is your hometown?"

The city is shaped by those who have moved there from various places. I had conversations to explore the connections between people and the city of Berlin.

At a large atelier space in Kreuzberg with bright morning light, I was having breakfast and listening to the story of a woman I met at the Gorki Theater.

"Where is your hometown?"

I casually asked her partner, who has been living in the atelier for many years.

He replied "Czechoslovakia, not Czech Republic, Czechoslovakia. Do you know what that means?"

I replied, 'No, I don't understand it. What do you mean?'

A room in an apartment of Neuköln, where drawings are covering the walls and shelves. I came to ask the story of a woman I met in a printing workshop. As usual, I asked this question while putting on the voice recorder.

The women replied strongly:

"There is no such thing"

I thought it could not be, so I asked again.

"But since you to have grown up where you were, I guess you can follow your path and find a place that you feel is your hometown. Don't you remember anything? "

She repeated,

"Nothing, I do not remember anything."

I repeated as well,

"But ..."

I caught people who were available to talk about Berlin anyway, and so I asked about their narratives. After asking these two informants a simple question, expecting them to talk about their memories of some village in Germany, I got an answer that confused me. For me, who grew up on an island, my

definition of hometown was always closely connected to my birthplace, my country, nationality, etc. These were deciding factors from the beginning. There was no doubt. However they answered “....., that's why I became German.” after explaining about their backgrounds.

Nationality does not only relate to what is written on their passports. Some talked with fearless feeling about where they grew up, but said ‘But that’s not a place I want to be.’

In opposition, some showed sorrow about the places where they no longer lived, and mentioned those landscapes as places ‘where I want going back to in the future.’

Sometimes their landscapes are a blue ocean, sometimes they are places destroyed by conflicts. What struck me was that the ones who emphasized the stability of their hometowns don't show sadness about leaving. Those who left their hometowns based on fear or situations of conflict, showed sadness about leaving their landscapes and expressed a desire to go back, even if to an alternative place. Although our bodies were within the boundaries of Germany, the narratives I heard travelled around the planet. Some mentioned the loss of their homes, or the lack of a definable place to call home, but then talked about their decisions to settle in Berlin because they found a sense of home there. And visa versa. Those who grew up in Berlin mentioned transformations taking place in small corners in the city made them feel like they were losing their sense of place, thus they left regain a sense of place. Gradually, I realized that a sense of home is not defined from the beginning. Instead it relates to decisions one makes, and the magnetic power of growing a multi-cultural community in the city.

“Placelessness of Modern Landscape”

From the dialogues with several people born in the 1980s and living in Berlin.

“... Then tell me more about your town”

“Yeah, Porto is a seaside town, there are many iron bridges and it's a beautiful place....”

“Well, but you didn't live there, Maia in the suburbs, is a neighboring city, right?”

“Yeah, but that's a typical modern city, it's not an interesting place to talk about.”

“Here, look, look at this picture, a house near my place, ivies growing in this car, it is left as it is. The city's construction started during the 60s, apartments were constructed during the 60s, looks like those GDR time apartments. That house (picture) is an exception, this is only one house which has its own garden, the rest of all is apartments, I grew up in one of them....the transformation happened so fast, during the 60s and before the 60s, there were only those houses in the area— . But you still see those small house around the corner, just gives you a kind of nice feeling about the background of this district.”

I sensed the incompatibility in their narratives about “Modern cityscape” originated from different parts of the world.

While some talked about the scenic aspects of their places, there were cityscapes built after the 60s urban development era, hiding behind their words. Some tried to tell me about the gap between the unfriendly landscape and their depressive feelings of trying to gain a sense of place. Some just neglected to explain those 'boring' cityscapes, by focusing on something more picturesque.

I wonder if this consolation and unfamiliarity towards anonymous landscapes might be the reality of modern landscapes.

“How do people perceive the current city”

Some people mentioned something visible and quantifiable, such as jobs, friends, parks, activities and the city's physical structure. Some talked about invisible factors like 'Genius loci', such as overcoming tragic historical aspects of the site.

"The negative power of the site gives me pain."

One informant mentioned the pain of encountering evidence of the catastrophe, on small paths via small metal plates with the names of victims, even though her family doesn't have a direct connection into those happenings.

The effect of public interventions concerning recent history is often mentioned.

"I don't care about architectural aspects of the city, but I felt I must do something here. I don't know, it's just nearly a sixth sense, there are no concrete reasons." said one who lost grandparents through the genocide, without hateful nuance.

For me, the surface of the current city didn't show so many negative sides of history. The negative history of a site could be a factor in deciding to leave, however other comments suggested that it could also be a factor in deciding to stay.

I had a strong desire to know how people reconcile past happenings, and how stories of place reveal those heavy topics, even when you don't expect it.

“The future place to live”

Through the transitional narratives based on one's background, to one's perception towards one's current city, informants reached the topic of living places in the future. Popular reactions were "I'm living in the city." Then "I don't know, but I may be living somewhere else, far from here." These were all long distance future visions from their imaginations. In most cases, the narratives of the past were stronger than that of the present or the future. A few reacted 'I don't want to talk about the past so much, let's talk about the present, I'm not a grandpa.' Talking about the memory of a place evokes the feeling of living in the past. Although my expectation was that people would tell me they were either 'staying or going back', they also talked about unrelated, imaginative places, mostly based on idyllic images of nature. While listening to these narratives, I noticed commonalities between them, such as landscape elements or feelings towards places. Although I thought that there was a correlation between their ambiguous landscapes and the words that they used, their hands stopped while drawing a collective image of their hometowns.

What absence reveals

When someone shares something, it means she is motivated by the desire for others to know. I encountered many moments which remind a classical theory of Johari Window while having interviews. There is an intentional “window of liberation. The act of dialogue creates a situation in which self disclosure is repeatedly opening and closing. There is a “hidden window” created by a hidden self who wants to conceal information. The speaker does not realize that the “hidden window” is visible but the observer knows there is a blind spot. With the “window unknown” scenario neither the speaker nor the observer knows what is being concealed.

Everyone observes only the opened windows and is in the mood of knowing the whole thing. Particularly while acting out a dialogue, these discoveries and disclosures are organically generated, and informants and interrogators encounter something they did not anticipate. Below are examples of self-disclosure and blanks spots observed during actual interactions.

In the early stages of this research, especially while in Japanese, I tried to give a numerical value to the descriptions being communicated to me, thinking that would make my observations “closer to the truth”. In “Mr. Kumai, Nagano” I initially conducted a quantitative evaluation of his memory. Initially I asked him to evaluate the strength of his impression in five stages. At first, his evaluation of the “mountains” had a small value. Yet while we continued talking over months, he noticed that living surrounded by this particular landscape was the most important element of his place. He changed his evaluation to the highest value of 5 or even more, saying it was unquantifiable. This suggests that our dialogue about place contributed to the meaning he attributed to that place. Over the course of our dialogue, something from his unconscious was revealed to both of us.

In “Roppongi Parallels”, the informant emphasized the world he wanted to protect while eliminating aspects that he deemed insignificant.

In “Landscapes Narratives”, the informants, coming from various backgrounds, expressed complex and extreme circumstances. They shared intended narratives and also erased certain aspects of their memories.

There is an absence of narrative in “Nothing special town”, which is about the generation that grew up in the new modern landscapes. Although they were surrounded by somewhat scenic views, they are not particularly interesting talk about. They judged their landscapes as insufficient, categorizing them as sparse and representing typical, contemporary, urban landscapes common in various parts of the world. Some informants talked about other places such as Portugal, Israel, Turkey and Brazil. One informant tried to omit descriptions of his own place by saying that the town where he was born and raised is “what is called everywhere”. They continued to talk about other places.

There is Topophobia: the physiological rejection of the traumatic emotions caused by the horror of the place itself. Topofilia: Not only the positive aspect of attachment to a place, but also the strong negative emotions felt between people and places. An informant affirmed that: "I do not have a hometown." Even though I still tried to hear about her childhood memories, she said "I cannot see anything - even after maximum efforts, I would feel the smell of spices I have cooked, that scent is the only memory."

She never lived with her immediate family. She first got citizenship in Germany after she was already grown up.

I also asked a person who had fled to Europe for a memory of his hometown. The speaker refused to answer and talked about something else. At that time, I asked this question because I was so immersed in the idea of memory of places in the past, but his answer in this case suggested to me that the question itself was a form of violence.

"Loss of place" continues to occur day by day in the world.

In considering the theme of loss of place, there are two principal examples: war and disaster. War is destruction due to human conflict. Disaster is destruction triggered by natural phenomena. During my lifetime in Japan, which has spanned 30 years, we have experienced significant loss due to two large earthquakes. For those who lived in the affected areas, everyday life was not easily restored. However, some people stay and try to restore places after destruction. Even if fleeing seems the most "practical" solution, many people stay and rebuild the site. Philia towards their places motivate them to do so.

Even in areas where earthquakes do not happen, war causes people to lose places all the time. If you consider this problem on a smaller scale, you can consider gentrification as the loss of a home. "Loss of place" happens on both big and small scales on a daily basis.

Portraits of Dresden

Place: Dresden, Germany, **Informants,** 14 random people in public space

“Portraits of Dresden” followed four steps in a sequential process. Firstly, I made questions based on my observations of the city. Secondly, I interviewed twelve informants who I randomly encountered in the city. Thirdly, I translated those answers into materials which are connected to symbols of Dresden. Then, I showed the plates, which were standing for the informants answers, as a kaleidoscope of abstract visuals. My initial inquiry which I used in my interview sheet was: “Does a fear of strangers have a connection to the love of one’s own place?”. Below, the backgrounds of these questions, the correlations between the materials and the answers, and the interactions between the informants and myself, are going to be further explained.

As a starting point for this project, political movements were mentioned as one of the central issues of the current city. I began by trying to avoid approaching people as either enemy nor non-enemy, and by seeking the common relationships between people and their places. There is a clear attachment to one’s own territory and a desire to protect it, that goes along with fearful emotions towards strangers from unknown places. I aimed to find the connection between the individual’s love of a place with the city’s larger phenomenons. By “making an artwork” in the public sphere— I decided to visualise individual opinions, converting them into abstract phenomenon, and show them as a part of the city’s identity. I believed the central motivation for those human behaviours was based on the territorial notion of the nation, the sense of community, and the fear and exclusion towards strangers.

It is commonplace to be frightened by unknown people, and to counteract when one loses confidence or the security of one’s identity. These attitudes could exist anywhere in the world. It demonstrates the strong relationships between people and places. Until this point, I had been considering Topophilia as purely positive. However, I started to recognise the possibility of negative manifestations of Topophilia.

In this project, I set up a questionnaire and decided what kind of materials to use. Then I made an analog algorithm to process the actual answer according to a material chart. My position was as a complete stranger. We gathered responses and tried to encompass the objective viewpoint of an outsider; an innocent existence as well. In the questionnaire, there were questions based on the PEGIDA demonstrations, elements I found in Dresden, and my observations of the city.

Fifteen questions were asked. These questions covered definitions of identity, relationships with the city, words used to deter people during the demonstrations, and observations from the street life. It consisted of those varied perspectives. The first half starts with simple questions and it advances to more suggestive questions in the second half. The general purpose of those questions was to place ‘doubt’ into the existing categorisations and definitions in each individual’s unconscious mind. Furthermore, when asking a question, I started with “I am ...” instead of asking “Are you-?”. The intention was to make people self-reflect more. When asking questions, I did not explain the background of the questions or the materials at all.

In this way I wanted to create the effect of a stranger asking you questions and then showing you your answers as a kaleidoscope made out of various materials, converted into a cityscape. I talked to people in different districts of the city and collected interviews. The questions were mostly answered in interview forms. Some of the questions, their backgrounds, and interactions are described below.

“Mein Alter ist ...” Mein Geschlecht ist ...

Is age and sex related to the connection to the place and to consciousness of others?

"Ich bin deutsch" Yes, No

This phrase carefully questioned the nationality of an informant, national consciousness, and identity. Whatever background they have, it is their subjectivity, rather than the law or any other objective indicator, who defines who they are. Although it is a simple question, some informants felt uncertain and started talking about the question and their opinions. From the definition of 'country of citizenship', all of the informants were 'German'. However I received answers I didn't expect like "Ja, aber...". They talked about the wider definition of being human, or European, and mentioned the critique of focusing on nationality.

"Ich wohne in Dresden" "Yes, no"

I hypothesized that the depth of the emotional connection with the city might not be proportional to the length of time in that city.

"Ich bin in Dresden seit" 1 day to 12 months, 1 year to 10 years, 11 years to 100 years.

The point here is to listen to different axes of time which are not represented on a line. From 1 day as a traveler, to 100 years of as an inhabitant, regardless of the length of stay, everyone is a part of the city.

Material: Leaves from trees on the street.

"Seit welcher generation?"

Options: Parent generation, generation of grandparents, generation of great grandfather, medieval, prehistoric times

It is a question regarding when one has moved to the city. From the parent generation to the prehistoric era (no one knows the prehistoric roots etc, but this is a deliberately exaggerated question), I asked in order to see how much connection the informant has to the city. When do people start feeling like a local? From which generation? What about when borders are changing? Who are the outsiders and who are natives?

Material: Pigment made from the topographical layers of Dresden

"Ich werde in Dresden bleiben für ..."

Options: 1 day - 12 months, 1 year - 10 years, 11 years - the rest of my life, generations of my own children - all descendants

I asked for two perspectives, based on planning and wishing. "How long do you want to stay in the city" and "How long do you need to stay in the city". Emotions for the city were apparent when the informants asked themselves, "How long will I be here?" Material: Animals related to Dresden

"Wenn ich das Wort Heimat höre, denke ich an ..."

Selections: "Dresden", "Saxony", "Germany", "Dresden is my second Heimat", "nowhere" "free description"

Before deciding on this question, I often observed various advertisements using the term Heimat in Dresden. Every time when I saw the word I wondered what people thought of Heimat and who the audience for these ads were. I was aware that I am not the subject of this catch phrase.

"Heimat seems to be a quintessentially German term, meaning hometown. It seems to have deeper nuance and relates to the ground and blood, more than hometown in English. But I do not know well, let's ask various people."

This word is often used in political activities. Initially, I made a prediction that the question of how much people are related to the site would be proportional to their sense of Heimat. But as I asked questions, people reacted in a different way. Some had no doubt about the question, and securely defined their Heimat. Depending on the person, the word itself was uncomfortable and they expressed their opinions about it. Some said "I don't have a Heimat." " But you're living in Dresden/Germany your entire life so far, even since your Great-grand-parents generation, aren't you?" " Yes, but you know, the term Heimat feels like 'Rootedness'. Not merely home or birthplace, but the roots. I don't feel my roots are here, I'm even wanting to go somewhere.'

Material: Metallic material (objects showing centrality such as nails and rings)

To be continued,

Memories of a place form your identity

What could our memories of places mean? Perhaps they are the tools which form our identities. Humans look to the past for various reasons, however, something we have in common is that we look back to gain a sense of our own identities.⁵

The self is expressed through memories. Where you were born, where you have been, and why, are memories which make up your identity. Sharing memories is important for self-definition even within communities which share a lot in common. If the memory is considered important enough to pass on to the next generation, it becomes history. These communal memories range from the size of a town's area to the presence of rural, national and ethnic groups. Regional archiving and the treatment of historical buildings shows how regions prioritize sharing local memories and present this sense of identification to the public.

Places are always changing. There is no such thing as "the correct form of a place". Places undergo not only physical changes but also changes in the way people perceive them. A place's image is not graspable. The only fact about places is that they are always changing and formless.

When human beings consider a place based on their own experiences, they often insist upon "the correct form of a place". For one person, their memory of a city 70 years ago is "the truth", and the current city's appearance seems to them a virtual space. To some people, the city's current iteration is "the truth", the history lurking behind it is somehow invisible, an old story without real feeling. This disconnect makes them feel estranged from each other.

When the past and the present deviate, those who live in the present do not have the skills to imagine the past, and those who take care of the past stubbornly protect their memories even though they are difficult to share. People also give up on actively making the future.

The same way that claiming "human love" evokes doubtful feelings, Topophilia sounds fake when relating to a big territory. It is necessary to use a small size to match the human biological desire and the abilities bound by sensation⁶. In addition, people can equate the region and the self more easily when a region seems to be a natural unit. Attachment cannot affect a whole nation because it is often a collection of heterogeneous parts gathered together by force. The modern state is too big to know personally.

5

⁶ Yi-Fu Tuan

Archiving unrecordable presence of a place

In the modern world, everyone can upload their everyday life to private folders on the internet. There seems to be no need to possess certain documents. Our everyday life is distant from the world of archived things in closed spaces. However I believe in the importance of archiving documents.

Images are overflowing everywhere, clouds keep vague information, everybody consumes images, content. What people show each other through their curated windows is not what we should focus on.

Inaccessible, but reliable, documents are protected inside boxes controlled by officials. Making unrecordable evidence of places part of an official archive is a small action to convert non-history to history.

My position in public space is that of an observer who then presents what I've found and deemed to be important for that area. Even if my observations don't have objective value in the economy or in local history, my motive is to collect and present that which has been forgotten.

Whatever one's process of making works, the process of abstraction necessitates cutting out elements and emphasizing others. It could be called 'Editing', 'Managing', or 'Artistic Interpretation'.

To tell a story, it is important to select samples from vast troves of information. Producing an aesthetic outcome needs control, like a dictatorship. This process has the same structure that is used to control groups. One must cut something in order to emphasize something else. By editing what was once unshareable, and only existed inside of your mind, you are making them shareable.

In/Visible Weimar

Place: Weimar, Germany

"Weimar is a cosy place. The community doesn't matter for me. I wonder what makes this mood."

As students from Turkey and Korea said.

"Surely I won't stay in Weimar. Of course I cannot find an interesting job here. What's more
Is that even though I have been doing many things here, I feel like there is nothing left.
Many familiar faces left, new students are coming. And the same things are repeating. I'm tired of it. "

As a student from Baden-Württemberg said.

Regardless of whether they are domestic or foreign, students are bubbles in this city.
They come and disappear as part of a repeating metabolism. They try to adapt to the city, make efforts
for a while, and leave for somewhere else. The real world, the bubbles, and the city's legacies of
classicism, are not intermeshing.

The archivist told me, "Documents about architecture which had disappeared are coming to our
archive."

Thus I decided to archive the story of the flat where we lived, with my own hands.
Gentrification is accompanied by sorrows where small places are lost. However, it is unavoidable to
be against the transformation and metabolization of a place. Having nostalgia towards a place is
part of human nature, but it has the negative effect of obsession with the past. I keep traces of small
everyday places that are not recorded.

This started with my own place, but there are plenty of places which are not recorded. It could be a
series of many Kein Denkmals.

The exhibition at the library is a specimen of ongoing projects.
The content is going to be stored in the library/ the city archive as documents.

There seem to be two kinds of landscapes in the scenery of the mind. One is the landscape of one's hometown, experienced as a child, sensitive and innocent. In this case, even a poor Bald Mountain becomes a nostalgic thing. This is similar to the imprinting done by a zoologist, and it could be said that it is a scenery imprinted in the heart as a memory. The experience of childhood does not change for a lifetime. If this scenery is lost without any trace, people will fall into the feeling of homelessness.

In order to solve this problem, it would probably work to leave features of the site, imprinted and remembered by the people, on the land as evidence. The place name will be the last fortress. Not only to leave a trace of the site as evidence, but it will be necessary to create landscapes that make use of it as a mechanism.

Another landscape inside the mind is, although partially overlapping with the first landscape, is a landscape that is considered common in all people's minds. These landscapes seem to be a number of pleasant sceneries which are modified in various forms, based on the landscape in which mankind occurred as a prototype.

The Visual and Spatial Structure of Landscapes

Tadahiko Higuchi

(1944-)

Shared places may suggest the future

In previous chapters, I mentioned memories of places, and my observations concerning the present phenomenon of place. Through the process of observing people's emotions, I had to deal with the deconstruction of my existing thoughts and the places that formed my identity. I realised that some of my previous works focused on evoking what was already gone. I need to use the power of visualisation as a tool to evoke the future.

Some people embrace the sorrowful emotion of trying to go back to places where we cannot really go back. I've often encountered viewers who are drawn to understandable drawings and look to those visualised traces of the past to confirm something. They are hoping to share their nostalgic feelings. Professionals, on the other hand, value abstraction.

I've often encountered affinity landscapes in Europe that seem familiar or nostalgic. For example, the fairy tale worlds I experienced in my childhood, which were pure fantasy at the time, somehow became synchronised with my reality in the future.

Nostalgia is normally defined as an emotion to evoke the past. Mostly personal, it can also be shareable. Literature and pictures can show us scenery we have never experienced. There is 'Nostalgia of the future' which may come from the 'Vision from the past'.

The future is a direction, the past is an accumulation.

If direction is indispensable for time,

the only time for life is the advance towards the future, the past is not time.

Aida

Bin Kimura

(1931-)

*In the large literature on environmental quality,
relatively few works attempt to understand how people feel about space and place,
to take into account the different modes of experience (sensorimotor, tactile, visual, conceptual),
and to interpret space and place as images of complex
—often ambivalent—feelings.*

*Professional planners, with their urgent need to act,
move too quickly to models and inventories.
A layman accepts too readily from charismatic planners and propagandists
the environmental slogans he may have picked up through the media;
the rich experiential data on which these abstractions depend are easily forgotten.
Yet it is possible to articulate subtle human experiences.
Artists have tried—often with success.*

Space and Place The Perspective of Experience
Yi-Fu Tuan

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